

On Data Structure of Graphs

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Abstract

Handling data structure of graphs for non-expert programmers is discussed and presented in this paper. Especially storing, manipulating and interpreting the data by using easily obtained application software such as Excel and an easily written program on C++ are presented.

Introduction

What are graphs? What is the usefulness of graphs? These questions may be mostly asked when paper presenting on graph theory. Roughly speaking, World Wide Web (www) is a **graph**. Every user is a **vertex** of this graph and connections between these users are called **edges**. Since everyone knows how useful the www and www becomes an essential part of everybody day by day, usefulness of graphs can easily be seen and studying the properties of graphs which is known as **graph theory** is one of the widely studied areas of computer science.

Another example of graph presented by now comes also from real world and very much acquainted for everyone. It is a road-network. A road-network can be presented as a graph. In the following figure we present a portion of road-network of Yangon's downtown area as a graph (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A portion of road-network of Yangon's downtown area

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Matrix Representation of Graphs

How to handle graph? How to calculate or find the properties of graphs by using computer? These questions arise when someone has to consider graphs which have so many vertices. Since a graph can be seen as an object in mathematics, usual representations of graphs are matrices. In figure 2, matrix representation of graph which appears in figure 1 is presented. We can see that if a vertex i is directly adjacent or join another vertex j , then there is a number which tells the distance between i and j . This number is the entry of ij (i^{th} row and j^{th} column) in the matrix. (See Figure 2)

But there are many entries which have only zero that means they are not adjacent or join directly one another. So we have abundance by using matrices especially when we have to input all these data in a file. In next section, we will present how to overcome this by using a data structure as exactly as a given graph.

Data List of a Graph

Since it is important to know which vertices in a graph are adjacent to which vertices and distances among them, we need for a given vertex that

1. How many vertices are adjacent to this vertex?
2. What vertices join to this vertex?, and,
3. What are the distances between them?

So a data list of a graph has to contain those information. In the following we give the data structure of the graph shown in Figure 1.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
1	0	160	0	0	0	0	0	40	165	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	160	0	150	0	0	0	65	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	150	0	155	0	95	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	155	0	150	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	150	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	285	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	65	0	0	0	0	0	155	0	0	0	270	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	165	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	155	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	280	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	155	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	280	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	0	0	275	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	280	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	0	0	285	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	285	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	285	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	280	0	0	0	0	0	155	0	0	270	0
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	155	0	0	0
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	0
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	310	0
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	0	0	0	140
22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	270	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 2. Matrix representation of graph

vertices	number of adjacent vertices	distance	adjacent vertex	distance	adjacent vertex	distance	adjacent vertex
1	3	160	2	40	8	165	9
2	3	160	1	150	3	65	7
3	3	150	2	155	4	95	6
4	2	155	3	150	5		
5	3	150	4	140	6	285	14
6	1	140	7				
7	3	65	2	155	8	270	12
8	1	270	11				
9	2	165	1	270	10		
10	3	270	9	155	11	280	19
11	1	155	12				
12	3	270	7	140	13	280	17
13	3	275	6	140	14	280	16
14	2	285	5	285	15		
15	3	285	14	140	16	275	23
16	1	140	17				
17	3	280	12	155	18	270	21
18	1	155	19				
19	1	270	20				
20	2	270	19	310	21		
21	2	270	17	140	22		
22	2	270	16	140	23		
23	1	275	15				

Figure 3. Data list of graph

How to input data lists in computer? One can easily input these data by using easily obtained application software such as Excel. But most algorithms for applications of graphs are using the matrix form (see Figure 2) of data structure. So we have to change data list to matrix form. It can also be easily done by following C++ program.

```
#include<fstream.h>
#include<iomanip.h>
#include<process.h>
#include<conio.h>

const int N = 500;
int counter = 0;

void initialize(float adj[N][N]);
```

```
void assign_weights(fstream & myin, float adj[N][N]);
void print_matrix(float adj[N][N]);

int main()
{
float adj [N][N];

char filename[30];

initialize(adj);

cout<<"\nPlease enter the input-file name: ";
cin>>filename;

fstream myin(filename,ios::in);
if(!myin)
{
cout<<"Data file not found. Program aborted.";
getch();
return 1;
}

while(! myin.eof())
{
int i, r, no_of_arcs, c;
float weight;
myin >> r >> no_of_arcs;
for(i=0; i<no_of_arcs; i++)
{
myin>>weight>>c;
adj[r][c]=weight;
}
counter++;
}
cout << counter;
getch();

print_matrix(adj);
getch ();
return(0);
}

void initialize (float adj[N][N])
{
int i, j;
for(i=1; i< N;i++)
{for(j=1; j< N;j++)
adj[i][j]= 0;
}
}
```

```
void print_matrix(float adj[N][N])
{
int i, j;
fstream diskout ("matrix14.dat",ios::out);
for(i=1;i < counter;i++)
{
for(j=1;j < counter;j++)
diskout<<setw(8)<<adj[i][j]<<"\t";
diskout<<endl;
}
diskout<<"\n\n";
}
```

In this C++ program, first read the data file (data list of a graph), then transform the data list to matrix form and store this matrix again in the computer. If someone wants to see or print this matrix, just use Excel.

An introduction book for someone who wants to know about graph is Bondy & Murty (1982) and we learn C++ programming from the book written by Hahn (1997).

Conclusion

Data structure of a graph must be used when someone needs to apply the algorithms of graphs for real world applications. It that so first encounters of difficulties is how to input the data. Here we presented that data file can be stored separately from main program and just use the application programs like Excel. So this difficulty is easily solved for non-expert in computer programming. Then second is how to change data to be in matrix form to compute it by a program. Here we give a simple C++ program to solve this problem. After changing data list to matrix form, it is also easy to print or read by again using Excel. May be we presented the very easy procedure for professional programmers but we hope that this may be helpful for non-expert in programming. Finally we also want to mention that the procedure presented in this paper comes from our own experience.

References

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- Hahn, B. (1997). "C++ A Practical Introduction", NCC Services Ltd., London.